

Title: Serial Dilution, Pour and Spread plating: A Simple Study on Getting Clear Bacterial Colonies

Pranab Dev Sharma^{1,*}, Towfiq Ahmed Disha¹, Utshob Kumar Debnath¹, Zakir Khan Rajon¹

¹Department of Biotechnology, School of Life Sciences, BRAC University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract

In this experiment, we tested two common ways to grow and count bacteria: the pour plate and spread plate methods. Our main goal was to find out which dilution level gives the clearest results for counting single colonies. We tested several dilutions, from 10^{-1} all the way to 10^{-8} . After the experiment, we found that the 10^{-6} dilution worked the best for both methods. At this level, the bacterial colonies were well-separated and easy to count (we found 65 colonies in the pour plate and 41 in the spread plate). When we used lower dilutions like 10^{-4} or 10^{-5} , the bacteria grew in crowded clusters, making them impossible to count. On the other hand, the 10^{-7} dilution had too few colonies to be reliable. Our study proves that for a clear and accurate bacterial count, 10^{-6} is the most effective dilution to get perfect single colonies.

Keywords: Serial Dilution, Pour Plate Method, Spread Plate Method, Colony Forming Unit (CFU)

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1. Introduction

Microorganisms like bacteria are very small, but they can grow into large colonies if placed in the right environment (1). Scientists use special techniques to grow these colonies and count how many microbes are in a sample. Two common methods used in microbiology are the pour plate technique and the spread plate technique.

Sometimes, it is necessary to know how many bacteria are present in food, water, or medical samples. But bacteria are too small to count directly. That's why it is important to grow them into visible colonies using these methods. But the sample containing millions of bacteria makes it hard to get or count single colonies. To solve the problem, serial dilution was used to thin the sample (2).

If the pour plate and spread plate techniques are performed correctly, there will be visible colonies formed after incubation, which means the presence of microorganisms in the sample. Moreover, if the diluted sample ranging from 10^{-4} to 10^{-6} is used, there will be well-separated and visible bacterial colonies that are suitable for accurate counting.

2.2 Serial dilution

To prepare the serial dilutions, we started by setting up eight sterile tubes, each containing 9 ml of nutrient broth and labeled from 10^{-1} to 10^{-8} . We first transferred 1 ml of the bacterial suspension into the tube labeled 10^{-1} and mixed it gently to ensure even distribution. After discarding the used pipette, we took a fresh one to transfer 1 ml from the 10^{-1} tube into the 10^{-2} .

This experiment is important because growing and counting bacterial colonies helps us in health care, food safety, and research. By learning how to use these basic techniques, students and scientists can study microbes more easily and make smart decisions in their work.

2. Materials and method

2.1 List of used materials and equipment

Apparatus: Bunsen burner, Micropipette (1000 μ l), Vortex mixer, Micropipette tip, Petri plates, Bent glass rod, Glass screw-thread tubes, Laminar flow hood

Reagents: 95% Ethanol

Growth medium: nutrient broth, nutrient agar

We continued this step-by-step process, mixing each tube thoroughly before moving 1 ml to the next one in the series. To keep the results accurate and prevent carrying over too many bacteria, we used a new sterile pipette for every single transfer. This procedure was repeated until we reached the final dilution of 10^{-8} .

2.3 Pour plating

For the pour plating, we started by keeping a flask of 150 ml nutrient agar in a water bath at 45°C so it stayed liquid. We performed all our work inside a laminar flow cabinet to ensure the environment stayed sterile. We labeled two clean Petri dishes for the 10^{-6} and 10^{-7} dilutions. Using a sterile pipette, we moved 1 ml from each dilution into the corresponding dish while sticking to aseptic techniques. After drying the outside of the flask with a clean cloth, we poured about 20–25 ml of the warm agar into each plate. We rotated the dishes gently to mix the cells evenly through the medium. Once the agar had cooled and solidified, we turned the plates upside down and incubated them at 37°C for 24 hours.

2.4 Spread plating

To carry out the spread plating, we performed all our work inside a laminar flow cabinet to maintain a sterile environment. We began by labeling a set of nutrient agar plates from 10^{-1} to 10^{-8} . Using a sterile pipette, we transferred 0.1 ml of the sample from the 10^{-1} dilution tube onto the surface of its matching agar plate. We repeated this for every dilution, making sure to use a fresh pipette

each time. To spread the liquid, we used a bent glass rod. We sterilized the rod by dipping the bottom part in 95% ethanol and passing it through a Bunsen burner flame to let the alcohol burn off completely. After letting the rod cool for about 10 to 15 seconds, we touched it to the agar where the sample was placed. We then gently swirled the plate and moved the rod back and forth to spread the sample evenly across the entire surface. After covering the Petri dish and re-sterilizing the rod, we followed the same steps for the rest of the dilution plates. Finally, we placed all the plates upside down in an incubator at 37°C for 24 hours.

3. Result

Previously prepared 25 ml of stock sample was used directly to prepare serial dilutions (Figure 1A). Eight small sterile tubes containing nutrient broth were labeled from 10^{-1} to 10^{-8} . Each tube received 1 ml of sample from the previous dilution to create progressively weaker bacterial concentrations (Figure 1B).

Figure 1: Prepared sample and serial dilution of bacterial suspension in screw-cap tubes. The image illustrates two stages of the dilution process. (A) A 25 ml plastic screw-cap tube containing the original bacterial suspension. (B) A rack of smaller labeled screw-cap tubes filled with progressively diluted samples. Each tube holds nutrient broth with a decreasing concentration of bacteria. These tubes are marked from 10^{-1} to 10^{-8} .

Colony growth was observed using the pour plate method at a 10^{-7} dilution 10^{-6} dilution. In the plate with 10^{-7} dilution and 0.1 ml of sample, there was approximately 10 colonies formed after incubation (Figure 2A). There were too few colonies (less than 30) to count. For that reason, the CFU did not count. Because this count is below the standard reliable range of 30–300 colonies (3), the result may not provide high accuracy. On the other hand, the plate with 10^{-6} dilution and 0.1 ml of sample showed a total of 65 bacterial colonies (Figure 2B). The number of

colonies were perfect to count and matched with the range. As a result, it was perfect to count the CFU for that colonies present in that plate with 10^{-6} dilution.

$$\text{CFU} = \frac{\text{Number of bacterial colonies} \times \text{dilution factor}}{\text{volume of culture}} \text{ CFU/mL}$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{CFU} = \frac{65 \times 10^6}{0.1} \text{ CFU/mL}$$

$$\therefore \text{CFU} = 650,000,000 \text{ CFU/mL}$$

Figure 2: Growing bacterial colonies by using pour plate technique. Two different serial dilutions were used to determine the growth of bacterial colonies. Very few numbers of colonies were grown for 10^{-7} dilution and a proper colony grown for 10^{-6} dilution. (A) A 10^{-7} dilution was used in the medium and very few colonies were formed. (B) A 10^{-6} dilution was used in the medium and perfect number of colonies growth is visible.

Moreover, colony growth was determined by the spread plating method at different levels of dilutions. A very high number of colony growths were observed in the plate where a dilution of 10^{-4} was used (Figure 3A). The colonies on that plate were too numerous to count due to the high concentration, and they formed clusters. In figure 3B, a dilution of 10^{-5} was applied for colony growth. But some colonies made clusters and were not countable. On the contrary, the plate with 10^{-6} dilution showed perfect colony growth. A

total of 41 colonies were identified from that plate, and there were no clusters (Figure 3C). The numbers were perfect to count and matched with the range (30-300).

$$\text{CFU} = \frac{\text{Number of bacterial colonies} \times \text{dilution factor}}{\text{volume of culture}}$$

CFU/mL

$$\Rightarrow \text{CFU} = \frac{41 \times 10^6}{0.1} \text{ CFU/mL}$$

$$\therefore \text{CFU} = 410,000,000 \text{ CFU/mL}$$

not properly countable

Colonies were clustered

A

Colonies were clustered

B

Single colony

C

Figure 3: Growing of bacterial colonies by using spread plate technique. Three different dilution levels were applied to visualize bacterial colony formation. Different numbers of bacterial colonies were grown at dilution level. Dilution level of 10^{-4} and 10^{-5} resulted the growth of many uncountable bacterial colonies. But, dilution of 10^{-6} showed proper single colony growth. (A) A 10^{-4} dilution was used in the medium and excessive number of colonies were formed. (B) A 10^{-5} dilution was used in the medium and countable colonies were formed but many of the colonies were clustered and not countable. (C) A 10^{-6} dilution was used in the medium and perfect number of colonies growth is visible.

4. Discussion

The main goal of this experiment was to see how well serial dilution works for growing and counting bacteria using the pour plate and spread plate methods. Overall, our results showed that step-by-step dilution is very effective at controlling how many colonies grow on a plate. This allowed us to get clear, measurable results once we reached the right dilution levels.

In the pour plate method, we found that the 10^{-6} dilution was the most effective for data collection. This plate produced 65 distinct colonies, which falls perfectly within the standard reliable range of 30 to 300 colonies. This range is crucial because it is high enough to be statistically significant but low enough to avoid overcrowding. From this, we calculated a concentration of 6.5×10^8 CFU/mL. On the other hand, the 10^{-7} dilution was too thin. It only produced about 10 colonies, which is below the reliable threshold. In a professional setting, relying on such a low count could lead to inaccurate estimates of the total bacterial population.

The spread plate method followed a similar trend, with the 10^{-6} dilution again providing the most reliable results. We identified 41 well-separated colonies on this plate, showing no signs of clustering. This yielded a calculated concentration of 4.1×10^8 CFU/mL. In 10^{-4} Dilution, the bacterial growth was so excessive that individual colonies

could not be distinguished, forming a dense lawn of growth. In 10^{-5} Dilution, there were fewer colonies than the 10^{-4} plate, many still grew in clusters. This clustering is a common issue in spread plating if the sample isn't diluted enough or spread evenly, as it makes it impossible to tell if a cluster grew from one cell or many

A major factor in achieving these clear results was our use of the laminar flow cabinet. This provided a sterile environment that protected our plates from airborne contaminants, which can often lead to false colonies that ruin a count. Additionally, our strict aseptic techniques, such as flaming the glass rod and using fresh, sterile pipettes for every single transfer, ensured that no bacteria were carried over between dilution steps. Those steps helped to maintain the integrity of our data. Several key precautions ensured the integrity of the data:

- The bent glass rod was flamed before and after each use to prevent cross-contamination.
- The rod was cooled for 10–15 seconds after flaming to avoid killing the bacteria upon contact.
- Fresh sterile pipettes were used for every transfer to prevent carrying over excess bacteria between dilution stages.
- All agar plates were clearly labeled and handled gently to avoid mix-ups or surface damage.

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- Surfaces and hands were cleaned before and after the work to maintain overall hygiene.

Testing more complex environmental samples, such as soil or water would help to evaluate how different microbial communities respond to these isolation techniques. The integration of automated colony counters could increase the precision of data while reducing the potential for human error during the counting process. Testing various types of selective or differential growth media would also allow for the identification of specific bacterial species rather than just calculating total viable counts. Additionally, adjusting incubation parameters like temperature and time could provide further insight into how environmental variables affect colony formation.

5. Conclusion

The experiment confirmed that both pour and spread plate methods can successfully grow bacterial colonies when proper dilution is used. Dilution level 10^{-6} produced well-separated, and countable colonies. This experiment shows the important role of the techniques and accurate dilution in achieving reliable microbiological results.

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Biosafety and Compliance

This experiment was conducted in accordance with the standard biosafety guidelines of the BRAC University microbiology laboratory. As the study involved only non-pathogenic bacterial strains for educational purposes and did not involve human participants or vertebrate animals, formal ethical approval was not required.

Conflict of interest

None

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